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The tantric concept in “Vātāpi Gaṇapatim bhaje”-A study

Dr.Pradeep Varma.P.K¹

Abstract

This essay's major objective is to explain the tantric idea that Muthuswamidikshitar used in his composition Vātāpi Gaṇapatim Bhaje. The genius of Sri Muthuswami Dikshitar was that he was a wonderful combination of a versatile composer skilled in many different types of unique music, a towering scholar in Sanskrit, which endowed his music with grace, dignity, and tranquillity, and a Sadhaka immersed in devotion and excellent tradition. In his writings, Dikshitar used Saiva, Saktha, Gaṇapatya, astrological, and Vedantic themes. This article's methodology is an analytical and descriptive approach.

Key Words

Guruguha, Ganesa, Hamsadhwani, Krithis, Mooldharachakra, parā, paśyantī, maddhyamā, vaikharī, Pranava, Parasakthi, Ragamudra, Suddharagamudra, Sabdabrahman, Sphota, Vaiyakaranas.

Introduction

Muthuswami Dikshita

One of the three great composers of Carnatic music is the South Indian poet and musician Dikshitar. His works, of which 500 are generally recognized, are renowned for their intricate and poetic depictions of Hindu deities and temples as well as for capturing the essence of the raga forms with the vainika style that emphasizes gamakas. Usually, they move at a more leisurely pace. In addition to Guruguha, which is also his mudra and appears in each of his songs, he is also well-known by that name. His works are frequently

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performed and sung in Carnatic music concerts.

He was born in Tiruvarur of Tanjavur distict of Tamil Nadu as the eldest son of Ramaswami Dikshitar and Subamma. After the couple prayed in Vaitheeswaran Koil's temple for a child, Muttuswami is supposed to have been born to them. Muttuswami Dikshitar was born in the manmatha year, in the month of Panguni, under the asterism Krittikaa, according to Subbarama Dikshitar. He was given the name Muttukumaraswamy in honor of the temple god. He also had a sister, Balambal, and two younger brothers, Baluswami and Chinnaswami. He is believed to be the originator of Hamsadhvaniraga.

His writings can be divided into vibhakti krithis (Thiruthani Guruguhakrithis), Thyagarajavibhakthikrithis, Navavaranakrithis, Navagraha Krithis., Kanchipuram krithis, Venkatachala krithis, Panchalinga Sthala krithis, Nilotpalamba vibhakti Krithis, Samvadi Vivadi ragakrithis, Ganesa krithis etc.

The tantric concept in “Vātāpi Gaṇapatim bhaje”

Dikshitar has composed twenty-three works in praise of Lord Ganapati. All the thirty-two aspects of Lord Ganesha or the elephant god have been praised by Dikshita. But only about twenty-three works are available today.

“Ajaṁ nirvvikalpam nirākāramekaṁ
Nirānandamānandamadvaitapūrṇaṁ
Paraṁ nirguṇaṁ nirviśeṣaṁ nirīhaṁ
Parabrahmarūpaṁ Gaṇeśaṁ bhajema”

(Ganesapurana – Upasanakhanda 13/3)

The formless soul is worshipped in Sri gaṇeśapurāna as an elephant's face and a human body. Pranava is symbolically represented by the figure of Lord Ganesha. As a result, it is revered throughout all of India. The two main languages in India are Sanskrit and Tamil. In both languages, the sign for pranava is essentially the same.

In Sanskrit, it resembles the face of an elephant with the trunk raised, but in Tamil, it is the form with the trunk lowered. Shabda Brahman is the subtle vibrating form of Parabrahmasatta, which is the basis of the creation of the universe. Om or Pranava is the symbol of Shabda Brahman. Patanjali stated that “Tasya vācakaḥ praṇavaḥ” (Patanjalayogasutra-1/27) in the Yoga Sutra. All mantras are chanted with ‘om’. Ganesha is given the position of Pranava in the mantras of all good deeds. Lord Ganesha is worshiped in the form of ‘Shabda Brahmasvarupa’. Pranava is the location of the three powers of the Parasakti. By worshiping Lord Ganapati, these powers are awakened and the course of life becomes smooth.

There is a famous story that depicts Goddess Parvathi Devi taking the soil from her body before taking a bath and creating a child. According to Yoga Shastra, Ganesh is the lord of the ‘Mooladhara Chakra’, the power center at the bottom of the spine. ‘Prithvi’ is the principle of the ‘Mooladharachakra’. In the work “sid’dhivināyakam aniśam” we find that “sid’dhamūlapaṅkajamadhyastham” (Composition Sidhivinayakam- Chamara raga, Roopaka thala).

Tantriks refer to this with the bija mantra ‘lam’. It can be seen that there is a similarity between this yogic principles and the story. Ganesha Tapini Upanishad states very clearly the reason why Lord Ganesha takes the form of Gajarupa, “tataśca om iti dhvanirabhūt sa vai gajākāraḥ”. That’s why the Upanishad states that “hari om namaste gaṇapataye tvameva pratyakṣam tattvamasi. tvameva kevalam kartāsi. tvameva kevalam dhartāsi. tvameva

kevalam hartāsi. tvameva khalvidam brahmāsi.tvam sākṣādātmāsi” (Ganapathyupanishad- Mantra 1). Muthuswami Dikshitar said that it is ‘viśvakāraṇam’. According to the Ganesa Purana, Ganesa created the ‘panchabhuthas’ and the world (Ganesapurana- Upasanakhandā 13/5,11).

Before the worship (Puja), the Tantrikas assume ‘Shiva’ on the head and ‘Ganeshā’ on the ‘mooladhara’ as “svasti śivādiśrīgurubhyo namaḥ, om̐ gaṁ gaṇapataye namaḥ, guṁ gurubhyo namaḥ, gaṁ gaṇapataye namaḥ, paṁ parameātmane namaḥ”. Tantrikas raise the ‘Mooladharachaitanya’ i.e., ‘Pranavaswarupa’ in him to ‘Dvadashanthapadma’, meditate and bring it back to ‘Mooladhara’, raise it through ‘Pingala’ and uplift it to the ‘Anahata Chakra’. After that, along with ‘jalagandhādi’ (with water, incense, and other accompaniments), the power is Invoked into the idol. In fact, the original ‘Pranavachaitanyam’ is Para itself. ‘Parachaitanya’ resides at the ‘Mooladharachakra’ of every living soul and emanates from the individual in the form of speech. Therefore, Dikshitar states that it is Lord Ganapati himself who shines in all four forms of ‘Para-Pashyanti-Madhma-Vaikhari’. These four states are manifested in the four ‘adharachakras’.

ॐ	parā	mūlādhāracakra	भूः
ऐं	paśyantī	maṇipūrakacakra	भुवः
ह्रीं	mad’dhyamā	anāhatacakra	स्वः
श्रीं	vaikharī	viśud’dhicakra	महः

In Manjusha text Nagesabhata states that “parā vānmūlacakrasthā paśyantī nābhisansthitā hṛdisthā mad’dhyamā jñeyā vaikharī kaṇṭhadeśagā” (Paramalaghumanjusha- Sphotanirupanam, Page. No-94) and All letters, words, and phrases are parts of ‘Pranava’, so ‘Pranavasvarupa’ itself shines in the form of words. Sreemadbhagavata Quotes that “oṅkārādvyañjitasparśasvarošmāntasthabhūṣitām” (Sreemadbhagavathapurānam-11/21/39). ‘Vaiyakaranas’ render it with the word ‘sphota’. It is a key concept in the Indian grammatical tradition of Vyakarana, and it refers to the problem of speech

production, or how the mind organizes linguistic units into coherent discourse and meaning. Nageshbhatta explains in Laghumanjusha that “sa cāyaṁ sphoṭaḥ āntarapraṇavarūpaḥ” (Laghumanjusha-Sphotanirupanam-Page.No-577).

It can be understood from the usage “trikoṇa maddhya gataṁ” that Muthuswami dikshitar was well-versed in ‘gāṇapatya tantraśāstra’ well. According to ‘Ganapatyatantra’ Ganesha is located at ‘Moolādhar atrikonabindu.’ The Ganesathapinyupanishad says that- “athādhiṣṭhānam ; madhye binduṁ trikoṇaṁ tadanu ṛtugaṇaṁ vasudalaṁ dvādaśaraṁ ṣoḍaśakarnīketi” (Ganesathapinyupanishad-2/4). It can also be interpreted on the basis of ‘Shaktatantra.’ In Sree Chakraworship, the Bindu stands in middle of the thrikona, which is the confluence of the ‘Shivashakti chakras. Three ‘Bindus’, namely ‘Shvetabindu’, ‘Raktabindu’, and ‘Mishrabindu’, are situated at this ‘parabindu’. Shwetabindu is considered as ‘Shivatmaka’ and Raktabindu as ‘Shaktyaatmika’. Mishrabindu is the unique state of ‘Shiva Shakti’. The mixed dot of white and red colours is created from these two dots. These colours can also be seen in the Ganesha concept. A delicate pulse called Pranava is given the colour white. Lord Ganesha is therefore referred to as ‘Shashivarna’. When ‘Vyashtipranava’ takes form from Pranava, which results in creation, everything turns crimson.

‘Hansadhvanirāga’ and ‘Ajapāmantra’

The hymn Dikshitar Vatapi concludes with Hamsadhvani bhushithaherambam. ‘sohaṁ hansaḥ, hansaḥ sohaṁ is the Synchronization with ‘Prana’ and ‘Apana’. That is where life exists. Because of this, the relationship between the ‘Mooladhara’ and the ‘Sahasrara’ emerges. ‘Vātāpi’ is composed in ‘Hamsadhvani’ raga. Yogis place all the letters in the bases (ādhārasthānaññal) of the merudanda. Sakara(स) is located in Muladhara and Hakara (ह) in Ajna Chakra. The spinal cord connects it. This nadi is the channel of the entire life force. The right piṅgala flows upwards and the left Ida flows downwards. All knowledge reaches the intellect through ‘Piṅgala’. From there instructions flow through Ida.

Breathing in and out of breath, every living being chants “Soham Hamsah, Hamsah Soham”, that Brahman is I, I am that Brahman. This principle is explained in ‘Dhyānabindūpaniṣad’ as “hakāreṇa bahiryāti sakāreṇa viśet punaḥ hansa hansetyamuṁ mantraṁ jīvo japati sarvvaḍā”. The composition ‘Vatapi Ganapatim Bhaje’ is a ‘Pranavasvarupadhyanam’. Dikshitar is expressing the state of ‘Paramahamsa’ through the tune ‘Hamsadhvani’. So we can assume that the word ‘paramahamsadhvani’ becomes ‘hamsadhvani’ like Devadatta is called Datta (Vyakaranamahabhashyam-Paspasahnikaṁ “ Siddhe sabdarthasambandhe” (अथवा पूर्वपदलोपोऽल

द्रष्टव्यः-अत्यन्तसिद्धः सिद्ध इति । तद्यथा- देवदत्तः-दत्तः, सत्यभामा-भामेति ।).

Conclusion

We can see the effect of Bharatiyadarshanas in all the works of Muthuswami Dikshita. All eminent musicians have composed works in honour of Lord Ganesha. ‘Purandaradasa’, who is considered the father of Carnatic music, composed the hymn ‘Srigananatha’ composed in ‘Malahari raga’ for the first time to teach music students. Ganesha is the lord of ‘Dhaivatasvara’ in ‘Saptasvara’. Dikshitar has compiled a collection of works known as the sixteen Ganapati Kritis. Lord Ganesha can also be praised in ‘Siddhivinayakam Anisham’. The peculiarity in many of Dikshitra’s writings is that the ‘raga mudra’ is added to them without diminishing the literary beauty. ‘Hamsadhvani’ is mentioned in the form of Suddharagamudra in his composition Vatapi . This term was also used by Dikshitar to refer to ‘Ajapamantra.’

References

- Complete works of Muthuswamy Dikshitar- Dr. S. Bhagyalekshmi, CBH Publications, Nagarcoil, 2007
- Isadi Astottarasatopanisadah- Chaukhamba Vidyabhawan, Varanasi, 1991.
- GanesaPurana- Nag Publishers, HA/UA.(Post Office Building), Jawahar Nagar , New Delhi-7, 1993.
- Lalitha sahasranama Sthotram(Brahmavidya Com.)- Subrahmanya Iyer, Vidyarambham Publishers, Alleppuzha, 2005.
- Pathanjalyogapradeepah- Sreeswami Omanand theeretha, Geethapress, Gorakhpur.
- Paramalaghumanjusha- Nagesa Bhatta, Kiranavali Com., Chaukhamba Surabharathi Prakasan, Varanasi, 1991.
- Sri.Ganapathi- Srikant, Integral Books, Anandashram P.O., Kanhangad,1982.
- Sreemadbhagavatham- Geethapress , Gorkhpur.
- Sri rahasyam II- Pradeep sambhavi, Published by Pradeep Kumar, Prakash Printers 2021.
- Vaiyakaranasiddhantalaghumanjusha (Vol.1) - Nagesabhattacha, Sampoorananda samskrutha Viswavidyalaya, Varanasi, 1990.
- VyakaranaMahabjhashyam(Vol.1) - Patanjali Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, 1987.

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